

IMPROVING THE LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESPONSIBILITY FOR RESISTING A REPRESENTATIVE OF AUTHORITY

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On May 14, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, issued a decree regarding "Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Legislation System," highlighting the inconsistency between the social danger characteristics and severity of sanctions for committing specific types of crimes. It was emphasized that alternative forms of punishment, incentivizing norms, and public influence measures were insufficiently applied and ineffective. Tasks for fundamental improvement were outlined for the newly adopted Criminal Code.

With this decree, the "Concept for Improving the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was also adopted. The first section of the Concept is dedicated to improving criminal legislation, and in the fifth clause of the first part of this section, it is stated that "Effective legal mechanisms for preventing and eliminating crimes must be created, and citizens should be instilled with a high legal culture, educating them in the spirit of adhering to the Constitution and laws."

These tasks impose obligations on both state authority employees and individuals to strictly adhere to the spirit of legal compliance. The mechanism for regulating these relations will be defined by established rules. The powers of state authority employees will be specified in their job descriptions. Any employee can only act within the scope of their official powers as defined. Exceeding the powers outlined in the job description will result in illegal actions. As a result of such actions by an employee, a physical person's failure to comply with their orders or resistance may not lead to legal consequences. The law (Article 219 of the Criminal Code) provides for liability for resisting lawful demands of a representative of authority. It imposes an obligation on individuals to obey and comply with lawful demands from representatives of authority. Therefore, resisting a representative of authority as outlined in

Article 219 of the Criminal Code leads to liability for resisting lawful demands or obstructing the fulfillment of lawful duties. For an individual to be considered as having resisted, it must be substantiated that they acted within the specific scope of powers defined in their job description.

According to Article 219 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, actively resisting the lawful activities of a representative of authority while performing official duties can lead to criminal consequences.

First, let's focus on clarifying the situation related to performing official duties. It is important to note that tasks assigned to a representative of authority by law or subordinate legal acts are considered official duties. One particular aspect that requires special attention is the legality of the actions of the representative of authority. This means that in this case, the representative must be fulfilling their duties as defined (assigned) in legal documents.

In this context, it can be agreed with the opinion expressed by PhD, Professor M.Kh. Rustambaev, who stated: "The official duties of a representative of authority or an individual fulfilling civic obligations are aimed at ensuring and protecting legal order and social security, thus the instructions of a representative of authority or the actions of a citizen must be within the framework of the law. These service obligations stem from specific categories of laws applicable to representatives of authority."

If a person refuses to comply with illegal instructions (demands) from a representative of authority, such a situation should not necessarily lead to criminal consequences. However, in each case, it may not always be clear to the individual whether the demand from the representative of authority is lawful or not. Clearly illegal demands from a representative of authority (for example, if they have consumed alcoholic beverages or are acting outside their official duties) are exceptions to this.

Judicial and investigative bodies should first pay attention to this situation, meaning they need to examine whether the demands of the representative of authority are lawful, specifically whether they are fulfilling their assigned duties and whether there is any abuse of power. When studying the experiences of foreign countries, it has been shown in English judicial practice (case precedents) that during the proceedings concerning such crimes, the court must indeed evaluate the actions of both parties legally.

The reason we are focusing specifically on this issue is that the imposition of illegal demands or similar instructions by a representative of authority towards an individual can lead to the commission of other crimes by these

individuals in most cases. In some instances, this may result in crimes such as corruption or the use of force and infliction of bodily harm by the individual.

Actions taken by a representative of authority aimed at provoking an individual's desire to resist should also be considered illegal. Such actions can include exceeding the scope of authority, refusing to perform one's duties, and infringing on the dignity and personality of the individual. These situations must certainly be taken into account by judicial and investigative bodies. If the actions committed by the individual do not indicate the commission of other crimes, then they cannot be held accountable under Article 219 of the Criminal Code.

The second issue in the analysis is whether the resistance shown by the individual is active or passive. For liability under Article 219 of the Criminal Code, the individual's resistance must be active, and attention should be paid to specific circumstances regarding this issue.

Although it is stipulated that for an individual to be held accountable under Article 219 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there must be active resistance against a representative of authority, the criminal legislation does not provide a detailed definition of what constitutes active resistance.

Scholars in the field of criminal law have expressed their opinions and observations on this matter in scientific articles and textbooks; however, there has yet to be a clear legal norm established regarding this issue. Specifically, M.Kh.

Rustambaev stated, "Active resistance refers to actions by the accused that hinder a representative of authority or an individual fulfilling civic duties from performing their tasks, such as obstructing an arrest, seizing criminal weapons, conducting searches, restricting freedoms, etc."

The importance of accurately and correctly qualifying an individual's actions lies in the fact that if the act is not carried out actively, it does not constitute a crime, and in such cases, administrative liability may arise. In other words, accurately qualifying whether the resistance was carried out actively or passively determines whether the individual has committed a crime or an administrative offense.

The study of foreign legislation has shown that in the laws of certain countries, specific actions that constitute resistance are identified as grounds for criminal liability. In particular, according to the Italian Penal Code, if a person uses violence or threatens with violence against an official, this situation is established as a basis for criminal liability. A similar provision is also outlined in the Dutch Penal Code.

Conversely, in some countries' criminal legislation, any form of resistance against state bodies or officials is considered a crime, and in such cases, any act of resistance serves as a basis for criminal liability.

Based on the analysis of legislation, in order to ensure fair justice, it is advisable to clearly indicate what constitutes active resistance against a representative of authority in criminal legislation.

From the above, the following conclusions can be drawn: In cases examined by the courts regarding Article 219 of the Criminal Code, it is necessary to provide a legal assessment of the actions of the representative of authority who is the victim. In this case, it must be clarified whether the demands and instructions issued by the representative of authority were within the law or their powers.

Moreover, it is appropriate to define the term “active resistance” as follows: “active resistance refers to any actions by a person that involve the use of physical force, obstruction, psychological pressure, intimidation, and coercion,” which clarifies the concept of active resistance.

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